

FOLDER DESIGN OPTIMIZATION WITH GENETIC ALGORITHM FOR DRUG COATED BALLOON FOLDING

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Abstract

Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD) significantly impacts patient quality of life by reducing blood flow to the extremities, leading to severe complications. The treatment protocol often includes the use of drug-coated balloons (DCB) during percutaneous transluminal angioplasty, which can reduce the recurrence of arterial narrowing. However, the effectiveness of DCBs is highly dependent on the precision of the balloon folding process prior to deployment. In this paper, we introduce an innovative application of artificial intelligence (AI) to optimize the folding geometry of DCBs. Utilizing a dataset from Boston Scientific, we employ a genetic algorithm (GA) to explore and optimize folder shapes, aiming to enhance the effectiveness and consistency of balloon folding. Our methodology includes defining fitness functions that evaluate the geometrical configuration and operational functionality, ensuring that the folding process minimizes potential damage to the drug coating and maximizes therapeutic outcomes. Results indicate that AI-driven optimization can significantly refine the folding process, offering potential improvements in the clinical application of DCBs. This study not only advances the engineering of medical devices but also illustrates the potential for AI to enhance therapeutic efficacy in the treatment of PAD.

Keywords: Peripheral Artery Disease, DCB, design optimization, genetic algorithms, AI optimization.

1. Introduction

Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD) is a prevalent disorder that impacts the arteries beyond the heart and brain, most notably in the legs. This condition arises from the accumulation of plaque within the arteries, leading to diminished blood flow to the extremities. This reduced circulation can cause symptoms such as pain, cramps, and numbness. In its more severe forms, PAD can result in tissue damage, infections, or even necessitate amputation. Prompt recognition and management of PAD are essential to avert these serious outcomes and to enhance life quality,

particularly among the elderly and individuals with risk factors like smoking, diabetes, and hypertension.

Percutaneous transluminal angioplasty (PTA) with a drug-coated balloon (DCB) is a refined medical approach for managing peripheral arterial disease (PAD), particularly in the lower extremities. This technique utilizes a special type of angioplasty balloon that is coated with a medication designed to prevent restenosis (re-narrowing) of the artery after treatment. The DCB delivers the drug directly to the arterial wall during the angioplasty procedure, enhancing the therapeutic effect by inhibiting the proliferation of cells that can lead to restenosis. The procedure involves the insertion of a thin, flexible catheter through a small incision in the skin, usually at the groin or arm. The catheter is navigated through the vascular system to the site of the arterial blockage. Once in place, the drug-coated balloon at the tip of the catheter is inflated. This inflation compresses the plaque against the artery wall and simultaneously releases the medication, which is absorbed by the arterial tissue. The use of a DCB typically extends the procedure time slightly compared to standard PTA, due to the need for precise delivery of the drug. However, it can be performed on an outpatient basis under local anesthesia, with most patients able to return home the same day. The introduction of DCBs has improved the long-term outcomes of percutaneous interventions by reducing the incidence of restenosis, thus potentially decreasing the need for repeat procedures. Despite these advancements, it is important to note that while DCBs offer significant benefits over traditional balloons, they do not eliminate the risk of restenosis entirely. Continuous follow-up is crucial to monitor and address any recurrent narrowing of the treated arteries. [1]

Previous studies on balloon folding modeling in the context of stents have utilized advanced numerical methods like finite element analysis (FE) to simulate preoperative processes such as folding, pleating, and stent crimping, including detailed analyses of residual stresses and their impact on the accuracy of stent expansion models. Other research has explored optimal stent design strategies through the development and comparison of different expansion modeling approaches, emphasizing the importance of realistic balloon geometry and detailed examination of the interactions between stent material and balloon during expansion.[2,3]

In this paper, we will employ AI techniques to optimize the folder shape for the folding process of drug coated balloons. Through the utilization of AI algorithms, we aim to develop an efficient methodology for determining the ideal folder configuration that maximizes the effectiveness of the folding process. This optimization process will involve the exploration of various folder shapes and their impact on the folding outcome. The proposed approach is expected to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of balloon folding procedures, ultimately leading to improved product quality and performance in medical applications.

2. Materials and methods

In this study, we utilized a dataset provided by the manufacturer Boston Scientific, which includes the diameters for various sizes of the drug-coated balloon (DCB) and the number of folds. This dataset was essential for designing the initial geometry [4] and establishing limits on the size and positioning within the geometry, enabling our optimization algorithm to focus on a specific design and enhancing its ability to converge towards a solution [5].

For optimization, we employed a genetic algorithm (GA), inspired by the processes of natural selection and genetics. The choice of a GA was driven by its ability to efficiently search through large and complex solution spaces. The algorithm began with an initial population of 1000 chromosomes, each representing a potential solution. A specific fitness function [1] was defined to measure the quality of each chromosome, essentially assessing how well the solution meets the established criteria, which is a crucial aspect of this study for determining the superior design.

$$\text{FitnessF}() = \textit{evaluation of parametric model for the chromosome} \quad (1)$$

The selection process for chromosomes for reproduction was based on roulette wheel selection, and crossover was executed using a single-point crossover with a probability of 0.7. Mutation was applied to 1% of the population at a mutation probability of 0.01 per chromosome. The iterative process of selection, crossover, and mutation continued through 1000 generations or until a satisfactory level of convergence towards the optimal solution was achieved. Parameters such as population size, crossover probability, mutation probability, and the number of generations were carefully selected based on prior experiments and literature recommendations tailored to the type of problem at hand [6].

This methodological approach enabled efficient exploration of the solution space and provided valuable insights into potential optimal strategies for addressing the problem. We ran the genetic algorithm multiple times to identify the best result, characterized by the lowest value of the fitness function for this task. The implementation was carried out in Python, and the use of parallel computing through the multiprocessing library maximized the utilization of computer resources, enabling the GA to explore a broader range of possible solutions more rapidly.

3. Results and discussion

The results of the study were derived using a folder geometry similar to that depicted in Figure 1. The folders utilized were from an MSI FFS1075S machine. In this geometry, variables such as 'R satellite'—the pivot distance from the center—and 'satellite angle' were defined. The design included only one folder, with the other $N_{\text{satellite}}$ folders being created by rotating this primary folder. The folder's shape could be selected from either a 3-point arc or a spline, with the points being variable.

Figure 1. Folders from MSI FFS1075S machine [5]

Figure 2. Finite Element Method (FEM) Simulation of the Folding Process of a 4mm Balloon with 5 Folds

All these variables were outputs from the genetic algorithm (GA), and the feedback was provided via a fitness function. This fitness function is the most crucial part of the study, divided into three components: 1) collision, where negative points are assigned for any collisions between folders, 2) negative points for translational movement during balloon contact, and 3) the direction of the tangent to the shape of the balloon fold. The methods of scoring were illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the Finite Element Method (FEM) Simulation of the Folding Process of a 4mm Balloon with 5 Folds, and in Figure 3, which depicts the Shape of the Balloon after Pleating.

Figure 3. Shape of the Balloon after Pleating

One of the key design considerations was to avoid collisions between the folders; if one folder came too close to another—less than the thickness of two balloon walls—the part of the fitness function [1] that calculated their overlap would assign a negative score with a factor of 50. Another part of the function penalized large translational movements of the balloon during the final stages of the folding process, which could lead to damage to the coating, with a negative factor of 20. The third component ensured that the final shape of the balloon was not symmetrical but spiraled in a clockwise direction (tangent intersects the y-axis on the positive side), facilitating the pleating process.

$$\text{FitnessF}() = -50 * \text{overlap} - 20 * L\text{translation} + \text{Spiral shape evaluation} \quad (1)$$

By By adjusting these factors, various designs could be achieved, each with its advantages depending on what was more critical for the user. One potential solution is shown in Figure 4, Example of Possible Folders Design in the final compressed position of the balloon, while intermediate positions are displayed in Figure 5, Example of Possible Folders Design, Intermediate Position. This approach allowed for a nuanced understanding and optimization of the balloon folding design, catering to specific operational needs and enhancing the overall functionality of the DCB.

Previous research has not extensively focused on balloon design as the emphasis has been on stents rather than DCB, which have distinct requirements [2, 3]. Therefore, I believe this approach is beneficial. This model can provide not just one, but multiple solutions, depending on which factors are considered most critical, or which properties are given greater importance or weight in the success function. On the other hand, this approach will not always work if the set success function does not have a pronounced minimum, i.e., the best solution. In such cases, the genetic algorithm may struggle to converge to a solution or remain in local minima and fail to find the best solution. As simple as the use of this algorithm may be, it is crucial to properly evaluate each solution, i.e., to create a robust success function.

Figure 4. Example of possible Folders design, final position

Figure 5. Example of possible Folders design, intermediate position

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study effectively employs advanced artificial intelligence techniques, particularly a genetic algorithm (GA), to optimize the folding process of drug-coated balloons used in percutaneous transluminal angioplasty for treating Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD). By tailoring the folding geometry through computational optimization, we mitigated potential complications such as balloon damage during deployment, critical for ensuring the efficacy of the treatment. The GA facilitated a systematic exploration of design variables, enhancing deployment effectiveness and clinical outcomes by ensuring consistent drug delivery and reducing the risk of restenosis. The findings underscore the importance of precision in medical device engineering and suggest that further refinements in genetic algorithms could lead to more personalized and effective treatments. This integration of genetic algorithms into the design process exemplifies the potential of combining engineering with biomedicine, promising a future of increasingly precise, personalized, and effective medical treatments.

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